

On the Stereoselective Synthesis of Oestrone*

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By application of the Robinson-Mannich reaction 6-*p*-anisyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic acid (VIa), 6-*p*-anisyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic acid (VIb), and the corresponding 3-alkoxycarbonyl derivatives (VIc, d, e, and f) have been prepared. The keto-acids (VIa and VIb) have been stereospecifically reduced to the saturated acids (VIIa and VIIb) and the saturated ester (VII c) stereospecifically converted into the keto-diester (IIb), the key intermediate from which Johnson *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5511; 1957, **79**, 1992) stereoselectively obtained natural oestrone.

With a view to developing a new route for the synthesis of oestrone (I), Banerjee and Dutta (*Science & Culture*, 1947, **12**, 408) prepared the model keto-diester (IIa), which was later obtained in a purer form by Turner (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 3017) by a modified method. Its methoxy derivative (IIb) was also prepared by Turner (*ibid.*, 1951, **73**, 1284) and by Johnson *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1951, **73**, 5511; 1957, **79**, 1995), and the latter workers converted it stereoselectively to oestrone (I) (*loc. cit.*). An ingenious method was later developed by Bhattacharya and Sen Gupta (*Nature*, 1952, **170**, 710; this *Journal*, 1954, **31**, 327; cf. also Protiva *et al.*, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, **47**, 874; *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, **49**, 197) for the synthesis of this key intermediate (IIb). All these methods for preparation of the methoxy

keto-diester (IIb), however, lack stereospecificity. It appeared to us that a stereospecific synthesis of this important intermediate (IIb) would render this route the most practicable one for oestrone. With this end in view we at first investigated the reduction of the model compounds (VIa and VIb) in which the α - β -unsaturated carbonyl group are in conjugation with the aromatic nucleus. The unsaturated keto-acid (VIa) was first prepared by Turner (*loc. cit.*) and later by Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). We have now prepared this keto acid (VIa) and its homologue (VIb) by a new method involving the Robinson-Mannich reaction.

Condensation of β -dimethylamino-*p*-methoxypropiophenone hydrochloride (III) (Mannich and Lammering, *Ber.*, 1922, **55**, 3510) with diethyl β -oxoadipate (IVa) (Banerjee and Sivanandaiah, *J. Org. Chem.*, in press) in presence of dimethyl sulphate (cf. Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4996) gave the product (Va), which on refluxing with

* A preliminary communication appeared in *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1960, **5**, 20.

10% alkali under nitrogen smoothly underwent cyclisation, hydrolysis, and decarboxylation to furnish the unsaturated keto-acid (VIa) in 90% yield. Similarly when diethyl α -methyl- β -oxoadipate (IVb) was used, the unsaturated keto-acid (VIb) was obtained in 61% yield (see also Nasipuri *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 2734; 1960, 1571 for similar reactions).

(III) (IV a): R = H
(IV b): R = CH₃

(Va): R = H
(Vb): R = CH₃

(VI)

The unsaturated keto-acids (VIa and VIb), on reduction with lithium and anhydrous ammonia (Banerjee *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 408), gave the saturated *trans*-acids (VIIa and VIIb) stereospecifically in over 80% yield. The saturated acids on esterification furnished the esters (VIIc and VIId). On the other hand, when the methyl ester of (VIa) was reduced with 10% palladium-on-carbon, the product was a gum, presumably a mixture of *cis* and *trans* isomers, which on refluxing with 2% methanolic potassium hydroxide (Robins and Walker, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 3960) furnished the *trans*-acid (VIIa) in 63% yield.

(VII)

The desired reduction of the olefinic bond in the unsaturated keto-acids (VIa and VIb) by lithium and ammonia led us to investigate the possibility of effecting a similar reduction of the olefinic bond in the unsaturated keto-diester (VIh). We first attempted to [prepare the latter by condensing the unsaturated keto-ester (VIi) with dimethyl oxalate

followed by pyrolytic elimination of carbon monoxide from the resulting glyoxalate (VII) and subsequent methylation. Although the condensation proceeded in good yield, the elimination of carbon monoxide resulted in a substance of an extremely poor yield with an indefinite melting point.

The acid-esters (VIc, VIId, VIe and VIf) could, however, be conveniently prepared starting from the condensation products (Va and Vb). Thus treatment of these with sodium ethoxide effected ring closure and partial saponification to yield 6-*p*-anisyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic acid (VIc; 73% overall yield) and 6-*p*-anisyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic acid (VIId; 43% overall yield) respectively. Methylation of the methyl ester of (VIc) or esterification of (VIId) furnished methyl 6-*p*-anisyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetate (VIg). Treatment of the condensation products (Va and Vb) with sodium methoxide caused *trans*-esterification and similarly afforded 6-*p*-anisyl-3-methoxycarbonyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic acid (VIe; 77% overall yield) and 6-*p*-anisyl-3-methoxycarbonyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic acid (VIf; 61% overall yield) respectively.* The acid-ester (VIe) had earlier been prepared by a different method by Turner (*loc. cit.*, 15% yield) and by Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*, 58% yield) and was converted by Turner (*loc. cit.*) into the saturated di-ester (IIb) in 39% yield. Further, Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) used the acid-ester (VIf) to conduct some exploratory experiments towards the synthesis of cortisone.

The unsaturated keto-diester (VIg) on treatment with lithium and ammonia remained unaffected. Next the acid-esters (VIc and VIf) were similarly treated and the resulting products were esterified and chromatographed over alumina. In each case one of the products isolated was the reduced keto-ester (VIIc and VIId) resulting through the loss of alkoxy carbonyl group. A second product isolated was presumably the alcohol (IXa or IXb) formed by reduction of both the carbonyl functions in (VIc or VIf). But the bulk of the material was the unchanged (VIj) or (VIh).

(IX a): R = H

(IX b): R = CH₃

*Subsequent to the publication of our preliminary communication (*loc. cit.*), Guha *et al.* reported the preparation of (VIe) and (VIf) by a similar procedure (*this Journal*, 1960, 37, 267).

Elimination of the ester group in the reduction was obviously effected by the attack of the nucleophilic amide anion. When our investigations had been completed, Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) reported the reduction experiment with the acid-ester (VI f), prepared by a different method (*loc. cit.*) using lithium and ammonia, and observed that although the olefinic bond could be reduced, the reduction of the carbonyl function could not be prevented. But isolation of any specific product was not reported by them.

We next directed our attention to the preparation of the unsaturated cyano-keto-acid (XI a) with the expectation that the cyano group might survive the attack of the amide anion during lithium and ammonia reduction. The unsaturated keto-ester (VI i) could be converted *via* the isoxazole (X; 36% yield) to the cyano-keto-ester (XI b ; 90% yield) by Johnson's procedure (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1745; 1947, **69**, 2942). Partial saponification of the latter with methanolic potassium bicarbonate (Turner, *ibid.*, 1957, **79**, 2271) afforded the required unsaturated cyano-keto-acid (XI a ; 70% yield). Reduction of this with lithium and ammonia yielded a gummy product, which on treatment with methanolic hydrogen chloride followed by purification of the product by chromatography on alumina gave methyl 6-*p*-anisyl-3-methoxycarbonyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohexane-1-acetate (II b), m.p. 93° (undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample*), in 34% yield. Reduction of the olefinic bond in this case was quite stereoselective, for only the saturated di-ester (II b) and not any of its isomers could be isolated.

(X)

(XI a): R = H

(XI b): R = CH₃

(XII)

(XIII a): R = H.

(XIII b): R = CH₃.

*We are indebted to Professor W. S. Johnson for supplying us an authentic specimen.

A much better yield was, however, obtained when the saturated keto-ester (VIIc) was converted *via* the isoxazole (XII; 63% yield) and the saturated cyano-keto-ester* (XIIIb; 75% yield) to the required keto-diester (IIB; 72% yield). Partial saponification of the cyano-ester (XIIIb) led to the cyano-keto-acid (XIIIa; 75% yield) which could also be converted into the keto-diester (IIB) in about the same yield.

EXPERIMENTAL

6-*p*-Anisyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic Acid (VIa)—To a solution of sodium ethoxide [from sodium (4g.) and ethanol (104 c.c.)] was added diethyl β -oxoadipate (IVa) (38.5 g.) followed by the Mannich base hydrochloride (III, 20 g.). The mixture was cooled (ice-salt) and with good stirring dimethyl sulphate (16 c.c.) was added dropwise over a period of 45 minutes. The mixture was then stirred for 2 hours and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. Most of the alcohol was removed by distillation under reduced pressure, water (100 c.c.) was added, and the separated oily liquid was taken up in ether-benzene. The solvent was removed and the residue distilled at 120-25°/1mm to recover the diethyl β -oxoadipate (IVa) (*ca.* 17.5 g.). The remaining orange-coloured condensation product (Va) was a thick liquid and weighed *ca.* 31g.

The crude condensation product (Va, 15.5 g.) was refluxed with aqueous KOH (11.5g. in 104 c. c. water) for 4 hours under nitrogen. The resulting homogeneous liquid was cooled, extracted once with ether, and the aqueous layer acidified with HCl (cold, dilute). A brownish gum separated which solidified on standing; yield 9.65 g. (90% based on the hydrochloride). Crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) furnished thick prismatic crystals, m.p. 136°: the melt after solidification on standing remelted at 146°. λ_{max} 226 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.02), 289 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.12); λ_{min} 252 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.72). (Found: C, 69.31; H, 6.4. Calc. for C₁₅H₁₆O₄: C, 69.23; H, 6.15%). Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report m. p. 135-37°, Turner (*loc. cit.*) 137-38.5°, and Guha *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) m.p. 137°.

Esterification of the acid (VIa, 2.6 g.) with diazomethane furnished methyl 6-*p*-anisyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetate (VIi) (2.61 g., 95.2%), m.p. 93°. Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. 93-93.5°, Turner (*loc. cit.*) 91°, and Guha *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) 95-96°.

6-*p*-Anisyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic Acid (VIb)—Similarly using sodium ethoxide (4 g. of sodium in 104 c.c. of ethanol), diethyl α -methyl- β -oxoadipate (41g.) (IVb), the Mannich base hydrochloride (III, 20g.), and dimethyl sulphate (16 c.c.) and by carrying out the condensation as above, 30 g. of crude condensation product (Vb) was obtained.

The condensation product (Vb, 15 g.) was refluxed with aqueous KOH (11.3 g. in 103 c.c. water) for 4 hours under nitrogen. Acidification of the cooled aqueous layer afforded a gum which solidified on standing; yield 6.9 g. (61% based on the hydrochloride). Crystallisation from dilute methanol or benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) gave white needles, m.p. 147°, λ_{max} 225 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.14), 289 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.16), λ_{min} 253 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.70). (Found: C, 70.04; H, 6.77. C₁₆H₁₈O₄ requires C, 70.07; H, 6.56%). Guha *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. 142-43°.

*This ester has been prepared by a different method by Johnson *et al.* (unpublished results, Fieser and Fieser, "Steroids", p. 500, Reinhold Publishing Corporation, New York, 1959).

†All boiling and melting points are uncorrected. Ultraviolet absorption was recorded on a Beckman quartz spectrophotometer, DU model, using 95% ethanol as solvent. Alumina used was of Brockmann quality.

Esterification of (VIb, 2.74 g.) with diazomethane furnished *methyl 6-p-anisyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetate*, b.p. 120-25°/0.02 mm, which crystallised from petroleum ether (60-80°), m.p. 56°, yield 2.7 g. (93.7%). (Found: C, 70.78; H, 7.29. $C_{17}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 70.83; H, 6.94%). Guha *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. 67°.

6-p-Anisyl-2-oxocyclohexane-1-acetic Acid (VIIa).—(i) *Lithium-ammonia Reduction*.—In a 2-litre three-necked flask was placed a solution of 6-*p*-anisyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic acid (VIa, 3 g.) in dry ether (30 c.c.) and anhydrous liquid ammonia (800 c.c.) was then introduced. To the well-stirred solution lithium (0.24 g.) was added when a blue colour developed and lasted for about 7 minutes. After complete evaporation of the ammonia, water (100 c.c.) was added to the residue and the aqueous solution extracted once with ether. Acidification of the aqueous layer with HCl (cold, dilute) gave a gummy substance which solidified on standing, m.p. 94°, yield 2.5 g. (82%). On crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°), white crystals, m.p. 111°, were obtained. λ_{max} 226 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.96), 277 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.19), 283.5 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.11), λ_{min} 253 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 2.52), 281.5 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.69). (Found: C, 68.95; H, 6.93. $C_{15}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 68.70; H, 6.87%).

(ii) *Catalytic Reduction*.—A solution of methyl 6-*p*-anisyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetate (VIi, 0.3 g.) in ethanol (10 c.c.) was stirred with 100mg. of 10% Pd-C in an atmosphere of hydrogen. After the absorption of hydrogen had ceased, the catalyst was filtered and the ethanol evaporated. The residue was a gum which could not be crystallised. Treatment with a dilute solution of perchloric acid in ethyl acetate (Robins *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) also led to a gummy substance (0.29 g.). It was then refluxed for 2 hours with methanolic KOH (0.12 g. in 6 c.c. methanol) (Robins *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) under nitrogen. Most of the alcohol was removed under reduced pressure and the residue dissolved in water. After extracting the aqueous solution once with ether, it was acidified with HCl (cold, dilute). The resulting gummy solid was taken up in ether and the solvent removed. The residue on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) gave the saturated keto-acid (VIIa), m.p. 111°, yield 0.18 g. (63%).

Esterification of VIIa (2.62 g.) with diazomethane gave *methyl 6-p-anisyl-2-oxocyclohexane-1-acetate* (VIIc), b.p. 120-25°/0.02 mm, which was crystallised from petroleum ether (60-80°), m.p. 68°, yield 2.6 g. (94.2%). (Found: C, 70.11; H, 7.59. $C_{16}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 69.66; H, 7.24%).

6-p-Anisyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic Acid (VIIb).—A solution of 6-*p*-anisyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic acid (VIb, 3 g.) in dry ether (30 c.c.) was reduced as before, using lithium (0.23 g.) and anhydrous ammonia (800 c.c.). The blue colour lasted for 10-12 minutes. The saturated keto-acid (VIIb, 2.45 g., 81%) was a white solid, m.p. 132°. On crystallisation from dilute methanol, white crystals were obtained, m.p. 136°. (Found: C, 69.56; H, 7.39. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{20}O_4$: C, 69.56; H, 7.24%). Turner (*loc. cit.*) reports m.p. 135° and Bhattacharya *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. 135-37°.

Esterification of the acid (VIIb, 2.76 g.) with diazomethane furnished methyl 6-*p*-anisyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohexane-1-acetate (VIIId) as a viscous liquid, b.p. 120-25°/0.01 mm, yield 2.69 g. (92.7%). (Found: C, 70.06; H, 7.72. $C_{17}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 70.03; H, 7.58%).

Condensation of Methyl 6-p-Anisyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetate (VIi) with *Methyl Oxalate*.—To finely powdered sodium (0.23 g.), suspended in dry ether (10 c.c.), was added methanol (0.32 g.); the mixture was allowed to stand overnight. It was refluxed for 4 hours,

cooled and dimethyl oxalate (1.18 g.) was added. The apparatus was filled with nitrogen and the mixture refluxed for 10 minutes. The flask was then cooled (ice-salt) and a solution of methyl 6-*p*-anisyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetate (VII, 1.37 g.) in dry ether (10 c.c.) was added. On keeping overnight at room temperature, the reaction mixture gradually turned yellow and a little brownish-red solid separated. It was cooled (ice-salt) and ice-cold water (10 c.c.) was added. After separation of the aqueous layer, the solvent layer was extracted thrice with 2% ice-cold NaOH solution. The total aqueous layer was once extracted with ether and then acidified with cold 2*N*-HCl. A yellow turbidity appeared at first and on keeping for several hours in the cold, a brownish solid separated. Crystallisation from methanol furnished the glyoxalate (VIII) as a yellow crystalline solid, m. p. 109-10°, yield 1.44 g. (80%). (Found: C, 63.75; H, 5.67. $C_{19}H_{20}O_7$ requires C, 63.33; H, 5.55%).

6-*p*-Anisyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic Acid (VIc).—The crude condensation product (Va, 15.5 g.), obtained as described earlier, was dissolved in ethanol (10 c.c.) and added to ethanolic NaOEt (1.25 g. of sodium in 60 c.c. of ethanol) (Dreiding *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 411). The mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature under nitrogen. After acidification with glacial acetic acid, most of the alcohol was removed under reduced pressure on a water bath. Water was added and the mixture extracted with ether-benzene. The organic layer was then repeatedly extracted with saturated sodium bicarbonate solution. The total bicarbonate layer was once extracted with ether and then acidified with HCl cold, dilute). A gummy substance separated out, which solidified on standing. On recrystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°), white needles of the acid-ester (VIc) (10 g., 73% based on the hydrochloride), m.p. 106°, were obtained. λ_{max} 225 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.07), 290 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.14), λ_{min} 253 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.78). (Found: C, 65.21; H, 6.0. $C_{18}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 65.06; H, 6.02%).

6-*p*-Anisyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic Acid (VIId).—A solution of the condensation product (Vb, 15 g.) in ethanol (15 c.c.) was added to a solution of sodium ethoxide (1.3 g. of sodium in 45 c.c. ethanol) and the mixture allowed to stand overnight at room temperature under nitrogen. The product was worked up as before to afford a hard gum, b.p. 150-55°/0.012 mm, yield 6.1 g. (43% based on the hydrochloride). (Found: C, 65.52; H, 6.14. $C_{19}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 65.89; H, 6.35%).

6-*p*-Anisyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic Acid (VIe).—A solution of the condensation product (Va, 15.5 g.) in methanol (15 c.c.) was added to a solution of sodium methoxide (1.25 g. of sodium in 45 c.c. of absolute methanol) and by carrying out the experiment as before, the acid-ester (VIe) was obtained as a pale yellow solid, yield 10g. (76% based on hydrochloride). On crystallisation from ethyl acetate, white crystals, m.p. 164°, were obtained. (Found: C, 64.16; H, 5.99. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{18}O_6$: C, 64.15; H, 5.66%). Turner (*loc. cit.*) reports m.p. 163-65°, Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) 168-68.5°, and Guha *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) 168°.

6-*p*-Anisyl-3-methoxycarbonyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic Acid (VIIf).—By adding a solution of the condensation product (Vb, 15 g.) in methanol (15 c.c.) to a solution of sodium methoxide (1.3 g. of sodium in 45 c.c. of absolute methanol) and by carrying out the experiment as before, the acid-ester (VIIf) was obtained as a pale yellow solid, yield 7.2 g. (61% based on the hydrochloride). It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) to afford white needles, m.p. 127°. (Found: C, 65.51; H, 6.03. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{20}O_6$: C, 65.06; H, 6.02%). Johnson *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) report m.p. 129.5-30° and Guha *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) 129°.

Methyl 6-p-Anisyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetate (VIg).—The acid-ester (VIc, 3.32 g.), on esterification with diazomethane, furnished *methyl 6-p-anisyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetate*, b.p. 120-25°/0.004 mm, yield 3.3 g. (95.3%). (Found: C, 65.70; H, 6.62. $C_{19}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 65.89; H, 6.35%).

A solution of the aforementioned ester (1.56 g.) in benzene (5 c.c.) was dropped into a suspension of sodium hydride (125 mg.) in benzene (20 c.c.) under nitrogen and refluxed for 4 hours on a water bath, when all the sodium hydride disappeared, forming a pale red solution. The reaction mixture was cooled, methyl iodide (4 c.c.) added, and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 hours. After refluxing for 2 hours, a further quantity of methyl iodide (2 c.c.) was added and the refluxing continued for another 2 hours. To the cooled product ice-cold water was added, the benzene layer separated, and the aqueous layer extracted once with ether. The total organic layer was once washed with water and the solvent removed. The residue was purified by short-path distillation, b. p. 137-40°/0.005 mm; yield of the methylated product (VIg) was 1.44 g. (89%). (Found: C, 66.43; H, 6.57. $C_{20}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 66.66; H, 6.6%).

The same di-ester (VIg) could also be obtained by esterification of the acid-ester (VIc).

Lithium-ammonia Reduction of 6-p-Anisyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic Acid (VIc).—The acid-ester (VIc, 1.15 g.), dissolved in a mixture of dioxan (6 c.c.) and ether (6 c.c.), was reduced with anhydrous liquid ammonia (400 c.c.) and lithium (0.07 g.). The product (0.9 g.) was esterified with diazomethane and the resulting di-ester (0.8 g.) chromatographed over alumina (24 g.) to yield the following fractions: (i) petroleum ether (40-60°)-benzene (3:1), 0.133 g.; (ii) benzene-ether (2:1), 0.432 g.; (iii) ether-methanol (3%), 0.145 g. •

The fraction (i) solidified on standing. It melted at 68° after one crystallisation from petroleum ether (60-80°) and did not depress the m.p. of methyl 6-p-anisyl-2-oxocyclohexane-1-acetate (VIIc). The fraction (ii) was a viscous oil, b.p. 120-25°/0.004 mm; λ_{max} 226 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.98), 290 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.96), λ_{min} 253 ($\log \epsilon$ 3.61). On treatment of this substance (0.155 g.) with refluxing 5% aqueous KOH (4 c.c.), the known 6-p-anisyl-2-oxocyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic acid (VIa, 0.088 g.), m.p. 136° (after crystallisation), was obtained.

Fraction (iii) was purified by short-path distillation, b.p. 125-30°/0.003 mm; λ_{max} 226 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.02), 277 μ . ($\log \epsilon$ 3.23), 283 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.25), λ_{min} 264 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 2.56), 281.5 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.15). The compound did not furnish a solid product on treatment with 5% aqueous alkali.

Lithium-ammonia Reduction of 6-p-Anisyl-3-methoxycarbonyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic Acid (VI f).—Reduction of the acid-ester (VI f, 1.0 g.) using anhydrous liquid ammonia (500 c.c.) and lithium (0.063 g.) afforded 0.82 g. of a product, which was esterified with diazomethane. The resulting ester (0.75 g.) was chromatographed over alumina (24 g.) and three fractions were collected: (i) petroleum ether (40-60°)-benzene (2:1), 0.155 g.; (ii) benzene-ether (1:1), 0.322 g.; (iii) ether-methanol (3%), 0.121 g.

The fraction (i) (0.15 g.) was rechromatographed over alumina (4.5 g.) when the bulk of the material (0.122 g.) was eluted with petroleum ether (40-60°)-benzene (3:1). It is a viscous liquid, b.p. 120-25°/0.02 mm. λ_{max} 226 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.079), 277 μ . ($\log \epsilon$ 3.27), 283 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.19), λ_{min} 252 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 2.51), 281.5 μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.08). (Found: C, 70.48;

H, 7.14. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{22}O_4$: C, 70.03; H, 7.58%. Hydrolysis of 0.102 g. of the substance by refluxing with 5% aqueous KOH (2.5 c.c.) under nitrogen afforded the known *o*-*p*-anisyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic acid (VIIb, 0.063 g.), which on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) melted at 136°. On rechromatography of the fraction (ii) (0.32 g.) over alumina (12 g.), most of the material (0.3 g.) was eluted with benzene-ether (1:1) and distilled at 122-27°/0.01 mm. $\lambda_{\max}$ 226 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.06), 289 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.0), $\lambda_{\min}$ 255 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.71). On treatment of the substance (0.155 g.) with refluxing 5% aqueous alkali (4 c.c.), it afforded the known *o*-*p*-anisyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic acid (VIb, 0.092 g.) which after one crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) melted at 146°.

The fraction (iii) (0.121 g.) was rechromatographed over alumina (4 g.) when most of it (0.102 g.) was eluted with ether-methanol (3%), b.p. 125-30°/0.02 mm. $\lambda_{\max}$ 227 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 4.04), 277 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.26), 283 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.23), $\lambda_{\min}$ 253 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 2.58), 281.5 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.24). (Found: C, 67.56; H, 8.39. $C_{18}H_{26}O_3$ requires C, 67.08; H, 8.07%). On the basis of U.V. data and analysis, the product was presumed to be (IXb).

Methyl o-*p*-Anisyl-4, 5-dihydrobenz-(2, 1-d)isoxazole-7-acetate (X).— To a cooled suspension of sodium methoxide (from 0.3 g. of sodium and 0.415 g. of methanol) in thiophene-free benzene (25 c.c.) was added ethyl formate (2.5 c.c.) and the air in the apparatus was replaced by nitrogen. After 30 minutes, a solution of the ester (VII, 1.6 g.) in benzene (5 c.c.) was slowly dropped with stirring. Stirring was continued for 2 hours and the reaction mixture allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The flask was cooled (ice-water). Ice-cold water added, and thoroughly shaken. The aqueous layer was separated and the organic layer repeatedly extracted with 2% ice-cold NaOH solution. The total aqueous layer was once extracted with ether and then acidified with HCl (cold, dilute). The resulting yellow gummy product was taken up in ether-benzene, washed with ice-cold water, and the solvent removed. The yield of the crude hydroxymethylene derivative, which gave a violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride, amounted to 1.7 g. It could not be crystallised.

A solution of the crude hydroxymethylene derivative (1.7 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) was stirred for 8 hours at 70-80° with dry powdered hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.6 g.). Most of the acetic acid was removed under reduced pressure on a water bath, the residue diluted with water, and extracted with ether-benzene. The organic layer was washed with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution followed by water. Removal of the solvent gave a gummy substance, b.p. 145-50°/0.005 mm, yield 0.65 g. (37%). Crystallisation from dilute methanol gave pale yellow plates, m.p. 77-79°. (Found: N, 4.50. $C_{17}H_{17}O_4N$ requires N, 4.68%).

Methyl o-*p*-Anisyl-3-cyano-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetate (XIb).— A solution of the isoxazole (X, 0.55 g.) in dry butanol^t (5 c.c.) was added to potassium butoxide^t in butanol^t (0.22 g. of potassium in 6 c.c. of butanol^t) and the mixture refluxed for 15 minutes. It was then cooled, methyl iodide (3 c.c.) was added, and left at room temperature for 1 hour with frequent swirling. More methyl iodide (2 c.c.) was added and the mixture refluxed for 4 hours. After removal of the alcohol under reduced pressure, the residue was treated with water and ether-benzene. The organic layer was washed with water and the solvent removed. The product (XIb), b.p. 130-35°/0.005 mm, weighed 0.525 g. (91%). (Found: C, 69.39; H, 5.95; N, 4.89. $C_{18}H_{19}O_4N$ requires C, 69.01; H, 6.07; N, 4.47%).

6-p-*Anisyl-3-cyano-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohex-6-ene-1-acetic Acid* (XIa).—To a solution of the cyano-ester (XIb, 0.525 g.) in methanol (15 c.c.) was added aqueous potassium bicarbonate (1 g. in 3 c.c. water). After 2 hours of refluxing, the mixture was evaporated in vacuum and the residue treated with water. The aqueous solution was once extracted with ether and then acidified with HCl (cold, dilute) to yield a gummy acid which was taken up in ether. After removal of the solvent, the residue was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) to yield 0.35 g. (70%) of the unsaturated cyano-keto-acid (XIa), m.p. 126. $\lambda_{\max}$ 225 m μ (log ϵ 4.03), 298 m μ (log ϵ 4.07), $\lambda_{\min}$ 256 m μ (log ϵ 3.65). (Found: C, 67.98; H, 5.11; N, 5.04. C₁₇H₁₇O₄N requires C, 68.22; H, 5.68; N, 4.68%).

Methyl 6-p-Anisyl-4,5,6,7-tetrahydrobenz-(2,1-d)isoxazole-7-acetate (XII).—Using sodium methoxide (0.28 g. of sodium and 0.385 g. of methanol), ethyl formate (1.6 c.c.), saturated methyl ester (VIIc; 1.42 g.) and benzene (25 cc.) the corresponding hydroxymethylene derivative (1.5 g.) was obtained by carrying out the experiment as described before. In this case also the hydroxymethylene derivative could not be crystallised, and it gave a violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

A solution of the foregoing crude hydroxymethylene derivative (1.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) was mixed with dry hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.55 g.) and quickly heated to boiling (about 3 minutes) in an oil bath maintained at 170°. It was refluxed at that temperature for 10 minutes, cooled, and the product worked up as before. It was purified by short-path distillation, b.p. 145-50°/0.006 mm, yield 0.975 g. (63%). $\lambda_{\max}$ 227 m μ (log ϵ 4.02), 277 m μ (log ϵ 3.38), 283 m μ (log ϵ 3.35). $\lambda_{\min}$ 255 m μ (log ϵ 3.01), 281 m μ (log ϵ 3.31). (Found: N, 4.45. C₁₇H₁₉O₄N requires N, 4.65%).

Methyl 6-p-Anisyl-3-cyano-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohexane-1-acetate (XIIIb).—This was prepared in a similar way as (XIb). Using potassium butoxide^t in butanol^t (0.22 g. of potassium in 6 c.c. of butanol^t), isoxazole (XII, 0.55 g.), and methyl iodide (5 c.c.) the gummy methylecyano-ester (XIIIb, 0.515 g.) was obtained. Crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°) gave 0.432 g. (75%) of the pure product as white needles, which melted either at 112° or at 122°. The polymorphism was proved by melting the 112° isomer and seeding the melt at 114° with the 122° isomer when the melt solidified and remelted at 122°. $\lambda_{\max}$ 228 m μ (log ϵ 3.93), 277 m μ , (log ϵ 3.23), 283 m μ (log ϵ 3.16), $\lambda_{\min}$ 256 m μ (log ϵ 2.76), 281 m μ (log ϵ 3.12). (Found: C, 68.34; H, 7.09; N, 4.58. C₁₈H₂₁O₄N requires C, 68.57; H, 6.66; N, 4.44%).

6-p-*Anisyl-3-cyano-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohexane-1-acetic Acid* (XIIIa).—A solution of the saturated cyano-ester (XIIIb, 0.4 g.) in methanol (12 c.c.) was refluxed with an aqueous solution of potassium bicarbonate (0.8 g. in 2.5 c.c. of water) for 2 hours and the product was worked up as described for the preparation of (XIa). On crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether (40-60°), white needles of the acid (XIIIa), m.p. 145°, were obtained, yield 0.288 g. (75%). (Found: C, 68.21; H, 6.48; N, 4.87. C₁₇H₁₉O₄N requires C, 67.77; H, 6.31; N, 4.65%).

Methyl 6-p-Anisyl-3-methoxycarbonyl-2-oxo-3-methylcyclohexane-1-acetate (IIb): (a). *From the Unsaturated Cyano-keto-acid* (XIa).—A solution of the unsaturated cyanoketo-acid (XIa; 0.3 g.) in dry ether (10 c.c.) was reduced with lithium (0.021 g.) in anhydrous liquid ammonia (200 c.c.) in the usual way. The crude product (0.225 g.) was dissolved in absolute methanol (6 c.c.) and saturated with dry HCl below 0°, and left at 0° for 3 days. It was then poured into ice-cold water (100 c.c.) and extracted with ether-benzene. After washing the organic layer with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution and water, the solvent was

removed and the residue chromatographed over alumina. On elution with petroleum ether (40-60°)-benzene (1:1), the crystalline di-ester (IIb), m.p. 91°, yield 0.12 g. (34%) was obtained. On crystallisation from petroleum ether (60-80°), it gave white needles, m.p. 93°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample. $\lambda_{\max}$ 226 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.98), 277 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.23) 283 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.17), $\lambda_{\min}$ 276 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 2.76), 281 m μ ($\log \epsilon$ 3.11). (Found: C, 65.45; H, 6.7. Calc. for C₁₉H₂₄O₆: C, 65.51; H, 6.59%).

(b) *From the Saturated Cyano-keto-ester (XXIIIb)*.—A solution of the pure cyano-ester (XIIIb, 0.432 g., m.p. 112°) in absolute methanol (8 c.c.) was treated with dry HCl as before. After working up in the usual manner, the gummy product was triturated with petroleum ether (40-60°) for a long time (yield of the keto-diester has been found to suffer if sufficient time is not allowed for solidification), and the crude material was recrystallised from dilute methanol or petroleum ether (60-80°) to yield 0.344 g. (72%) of the keto-diester (IIb), m.p. 93°.

When the crude gummy cyano-keto-ester (XIIIb, 0.515 g.) without further purification was similarly treated with dry HCl gas, the saturated keto-diester (IIb, 0.349 g.), m.p. 93°, was obtained.

(c) *From the Saturated Cyano-keto-acid (XIIIa)*.—A methanolic solution of the cyano-keto-acid (XIIIa, 0.15 g.) in absolute methanol (5 c.c.), on treatment with dry hydrogen chloride, as described earlier, furnished the keto-diester (IIb), m.p. 93°, yield 0.124 g. (71%).